

The Concept of Ideal Strategy and Its Realization Using White Ocean Mixed Strategy

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Abstract

Strategic planning and decision making has an important role in organizational development and sustainability. Various types of strategies are used in strategic management such as Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Green ocean strategy, Purple ocean strategy and Black ocean strategy. These strategies are used in organizations by top level executive managers for long term organizational sustainability and to face or deviate from the competition. Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that many of the organizations use a new type of strategy which is derived from the above five types of strategies for sustainability. In this paper we have generalized such strategies by developing a concept of ideal strategy and named it as "White Ocean Strategy". Based on observation and focus group study we developed this concept and studied the conditions, characteristics and procedure of this model of decision making. We have studied the reasons why certain firms opt for White ocean strategy while making decisions for sustainability and consequences of such strategic decisions through investment/perceived Risk Matrix. We have also compared the different strategic choices with that of White ocean strategy. The details and consequences of such strategy followed in some organizations are also discussed.

Keywords : *Ideal Strategy, Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Black ocean strategy, White ocean strategy, Comparison of different strategies, Characteristics of White ocean strategy.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Strategic planning and decision making are important in organizations using business. A strategy is a long-term plan for the whole organisation or for an individual to ensure successful completion of any activity in a business. Most of the big business firms involved in national level of international level business develops strategy at executive level called corporate strategy. Corporate strategy is defined as the positioning and relating of the firm/organisation to its environment in a way which will assure its continued success and make it sure from surprises (Ansoff H. I. 1987)[1]. Several factors decides corporate strategy to emerge successful such for instance is growth, stability, profitability and efficiency. Growth involves the expansion of a business, its markets, products, services, size etc. Successful growth strategies are based on having the resources to support growth, identifying the markets that make growth worthwhile being better in competition in these growth markets. Stability involves a consolidation strategy for the organisation, often before a period of growth. The organisation needs to establish clear procedures and systems during this period before moving on. Seeking profit is an important business strategy, particularly in organisations where shareholders have considerable influence. Efficiency is concerned with how well resources have been used in meeting organisational objectives. It is important for public sector service organisations to show that taxpayers funds have been used well. This apart, market leadership strategies aims to grab the global market. The market leader is able to gain considerable cost advantages over rivals because by definition other firms will have a smaller market share and therefore fewer opportunities for economies of scale. Beyond all these survival is essential in a highly competitive business environment. Survival is the key to most organisations. Only by surviving they are able to develop other strategies. Apart from above, strategies of an organization or individual are divided into another class as (1) competitive strategies also called Red ocean strategies (Porter M.E. 1998)[2], (2) monopoly strategy called Blue ocean strategy (Han Kim W. 2006) [3], (3) sustainable strategy called Green ocean strategy (Hou, Shengtian, 2007) [4], (4) a mix of Blue and Green called Purple ocean strategy (Babelfish, 2007) [5]. (5) unethical strategy for one time survival called black ocean strategy (Aithal P.S 2015) [6-7] and combined/white ocean strategies used in this paper.

Think of the market as an ocean and the competing organizations as sharks fighting each other and striving to prevail. The bloodshed makes the ocean turn red. That is why the competing strategies followed by the organizations are called red ocean strategies (Porter M. E. 1980) [8]. Red oceans represent all the industries in existence today in the known market space. In red oceans, industry boundaries are defined and accepted, and the competitive rules of the game are well understood. Here, companies try to outperform their rivals in order to grab a greater share of existing demand. As the space gets more and more crowded, prospects for profits and growth are reduced. Products turn into commodities, and increasing competition turns the water bloody. Red ocean strategy supports to compete in existing market space, beat the competition, exploit existing demand, make the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost (Porter M. E. 1980) [8].

Blue oceans denote all the industries not in existence today- the unknown market space, untainted by competition. In blue oceans, demand is created rather than fought over. There is ample opportunity for growth that is both profitable and rapid. There are two ways to create blue oceans. In a few cases, companies can give rise to completely new

industries, as eBay did with the online auction industry. But in most cases, a blue ocean is created from within a red ocean when a company alters the boundaries of an existing industry. Blue ocean strategy supports to create uncontested market space, make the competition irrelevant, create and capture new demand, break the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost (Kim W. C., and Mauborgne R. 2004) [9].

Green Ocean Strategy is a recent strategic outcome with two different types of schools of thought. According to first school of thought, it is a strategy to gauge the impact of environmental footprint on human lives. From different unstructured documents like newspapers, magazines, world wide web pages, it is revealed that automobile industry happens to be one of the largest contributors of environmental pollution throughout the world. India, as an emerging economy, has become a lucrative market destination for automobiles. Due to high level of global competition, a plethora of global automobile players have crowded in this second largest market. This phenomenon coupled with influx of other industries has blown up the environmental footprint in India leaving an adverse impact on human lives [9]. According to second school of thought, it is a hybrid mechanism which combines the best things that characterize Blue ocean and Red ocean strategies. The keyword in discussing this theory is *sustainability* and there can be no one-size-fits-all formula governing the innovation mechanism of an organization [10 -11].

Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that some of the organizations and individuals especially in developing countries use a new type of strategy for survival and sustainability at least for short term to overcome their intensive problem and to get quick relief from the problems. In this paper we have generalized such a strategy and named it as "Black Ocean Strategy". Black ocean strategy is a kind of survival strategy to foresee the organizational problems and solve them successfully to continue in its business market by means of a kind of black magic may be legally or illegally, ethically or unethically. Based on our observation and focus group study we have developed this concept systematically and studied the conditions and characteristics of this model of decision-making called Black ocean strategy. We have studied the reasons why certain firms and certain individuals at its helm follow Black ocean strategy while making decision for survival and consequences of such strategic decisions through investment/perceived Risk Matrix. We have also compared red ocean strategy & Black ocean strategy, blue ocean strategy & Black ocean strategy, and green ocean strategy and Black ocean strategy used in organizations. Finally the details and consequences of Black ocean strategy followed by few organizations are discussed.

II. VARIOUS STRATEGIES USED IN BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

Table 1 : Details of various strategies used in business management

S. No.	Type of Strategy	Details
1	Red Ocean Strategy	Red ocean strategy supports to compete in existing market space, beat the competition, exploit existing demand, make the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost.
2	Blue Ocean Strategy	Blue ocean strategy supports to create uncontested market space, make the competition irrelevant, create and capture new demand, break the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost.
3	Green Ocean Strategy	Green ocean strategy to support the impact of environmental footprint on human lives. From different unstructured documents like newspapers, magazines, world wide web pages, it is revealed that automobile industry happens to be one of the largest contributors of environmental pollution throughout the world. India, as an emerging economy, has become a lucrative market destination for automobiles.
4	Purple Ocean Strategy	A mix of Blue ocean and Green ocean strategy is called Purple ocean strategy.
5	Black Ocean Strategy	Black ocean strategy is a kind of survival strategy to foresee the organizational problems and solve them successfully to continue in its business market by means of a kind of black magic may be legally or illegally, ethically or unethically.
	White Ocean Strategy (Danai Chanchaochai's Model)	White Ocean's concept is concerning about "social" more than "profit" that made WOS outstanding than the others oceans which is gaining reputation and profit from their customer by using any strategies to be apart or win the competition in market. The concept of WOS is focusing on People, Planet, Profit and Passion. Concerning in sociological and environment are most important in this ocean. Both WOS and Green ocean strategies have same objective of preserving environment and hence society.
7	White Ocean Mixed Strategy (Proposed in this paper)	Mixture of red ocean, blue ocean, green ocean and black ocean strategies for organisational survival, sustainability and profit.
7	Ideal strategy	A planning and execution strategy which confirms the success of the work in any situational conditions and constraints. This strategy ensures the sustainability of the organization with huge profit.

III. IDEAL STRATEGY IN BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

An ideal strategy is a planning and execution strategy which confirms the success of the work in any situational conditions and constraints. This strategy ensures the sustainability of the organization with huge profit. Ideal strategy always ensures winning in an organizational problem with least or zero effort. Ideal strategy is suitable for hypothetical situations to conform winning but cannot be implemented for real situations. But we can realize the consequences of ideal strategy in practice by means of the new strategy named White Ocean Mixed (WOM) strategy, which is an optimum mixture of all existing strategies like red ocean strategy, blue ocean strategy, green ocean strategy, black ocean strategy and white ocean strategies. The concept of ideal strategy is developed in business management like ideal engine in thermodynamics [12], ideal business model to study best characteristics of business system [13-14], ideal technology while studying the characteristics of best technology for human beings [15], ideal education system while studying the characteristics required for a best education system [16 -17]. Similarly the model of ideal strategy would help in deciding the characteristics of the best strategy for any business management problem.

(1) Model of Ideal Strategy :

Figure 1 : Ideal strategy model

A simple concept of ideal strategy is shown in the form of a block diagram (figure 1). An ideal strategy of an organization solves the organizational problems and gives perfect solution to fulfil its objectives. Ideal strategy is a hypothetical strategy which cannot be achieved in practice. But the existing strategies used in organizations can be improved or systematically planned depending on the problems and situations to solve the problems optimally.

(2) Characteristics of Ideal Strategy :

Even though the characteristics of ideal strategy cannot be implemented in reality, to develop an optimum strategy which will ensure the organizational success, one has to identify characteristics of ideal strategy. The important characteristics of ideal strategy which will give idea to identify optimum strategy to the organizational problems are given below :

1. The strategy should be independent on types of business and type of problems.
2. The strategy should identify ideal solutions to organizational problems and fulfil organizational objectives.
3. Ideal strategy provides solutions to all problems the organization is facing and gives expected output whatever may be the constraints of the business system.
4. Flexible to accommodate internal and environmental changes.
5. Success through ideal strategy is measurable.
6. Ideal strategy will not consume any resources while implementing.
7. Ideal strategy is easy to implement and supports to fulfil the objectives at zero cost and zero time without any constraints.
8. Ideal strategy includes competitive strategy, monopoly strategy, sustainable strategy and survival strategy to win the organizational challenges.
9. Ideal strategy translates organizational business into ideal business.
10. Ideal strategy guarantees the organizational success in any kind of internal and external environments.

(3) How ideal strategy is different from optimum strategy

Figure 2 : Block diagram of Optimum strategy model.

An optimum strategy is the best strategy within organizational or business constraints to fulfil the objectives of an organization. Optimum strategies of an organization can be realized and results can be tested. Optimum strategy in an organization or in a business model supports how to face competition, how to develop monopoly products and services, how to maintain environment for sustainability, how to manage turbulent situations for survival, and how to get long term profit for changes in internal and external environments. Figure 3 shows the block diagram of an optimum strategy model. Thus optimum strategy contains everything to do for organizational sustainability.

IV. WHITE OCEAN MIXED (WOM) STRATEGY FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY

(a) Concept development :

The study of strategic management literature tells us that there are five prominent strategies used in organizations to increase their profit. They are Red Ocean or competitive strategies developed by Michel Porter [2], Blue Ocean or monopoly strategies developed by W. Chan Kim and Renée Mauborgne [3], Green Ocean or Environmental sustainability strategy developed by Hou, Shengtian (2007) [4], Black Ocean or survival strategy developed by Aithal P.S. (2015) [6], and White Ocean or Social and Sustainable strategy developed by Danai Chanchaochai [10]. These strategies are useful and appropriate for different types of organizations at different environment. As we studied, in optics, white light also called composite light, is made up of seven colours, there should be a White Ocean strategy which is a mix of all other strategies to be used right amount, right time, to ensure organizational success. This mixed strategy consisting of all above mentioned strategies in right time to right problem is named as White Ocean Mixed Strategy (WOMS). White Ocean Mixed Strategy is an optimum strategy to solve any type of organizational problems, with any kind of environment optimally.

(b) Objectives of White Ocean Mixed Strategy :

- (1) White Ocean Mixed Strategy is a mixture of red ocean, blue ocean, green ocean and black ocean strategies for organisational survival, sustainability and profit.
- (2) Focusing all aspects of organizational problems by focusing on all the aspect like profit, monopoly, sustainability, environment, and survival.
- (3) White ocean mixed strategy consists of all strategies inherently mixed for optimum solution to an organizational problem like white light is made of seven colours.
- (4) White ocean mixed strategy gives equal importance to competition, monopoly, environment, long term sustainability and survival in a given situation along with long term profit.
- (5) WOMS supports each and every aspect of organizational success and hence will become role model to other organizations.
- (6) White ocean is a best strategy which contains mixture of other strategies depending the upon situations.
- (7) WOMS align whole system of firm's activities in pursuit of survival & win.

(c) How It is different from Danai Chanchaochai's Social white ocean strategy :

The difference between Danai Chanchaochai's Social White Ocean Strategy (WOS) and the proposed White ocean mixed strategy is listed in table 2. WOS is mainly focused on society and environment by overlooking the profit of the organization. This kind of strategy may pose danger to organizational survival. No organization can sustain without profit so that during the developing stage of the organization, identifying suitable strategy or mixture of strategies from the bunch of available strategies is important. Organizational survival is equally important along with environmental sustainability by implementing green processes & green services in the business. WOS is another version of already existing Green ocean strategy.

Table 2 : Distinction between Danai Chanchaochai's White Ocean Strategy (WOS) and White Ocean Mixed (WOM) Strategy

S. No.	Danai Chanchaochai's White Ocean Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy Used in this Paper
1	Concerning about "social" more than "profit" that made.	Focusing all aspects of organizational problems by focusing on all the aspect like profit, monopoly, sustainability, environment, and survival.
2	WOS outstanding than the others oceans which is gaining reputation and profit from their customer by using any strategies to be apart or win the competition in market.	White ocean mixed strategy is used for applying optimum strategy with in the given situations in an organization for survival and development through profit.
3	The concept of WOS is focusing on People, Planet, Profit and Passion.	White ocean mixed strategy consists of all strategies inherently mixed for optimum solution to an organizational problem like white light is made of seven colours.
4	WOS process is taking care social and environment at first by overlook the profit.	White ocean mixed strategy gives equal importance to competition, monopoly, environment, long term sustainability and survival in a given situation along with long term profit.
5	WOS need not support success on business but the author gave a good role model of companies which have social and environment awareness.	WOMS supports each and every aspect of organizational success and hence will become role model to other organizations
6	WOS probably similar as CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) that recently many big companies enthuse about to show up their responsibility to society.	WOMS is more than CSR in the sense that it supports organizational CSR activities by providing higher sustainable profit to the organization.
7	White Ocean can merge in Green ocean to improve environment awareness.	WOMS is an integrated strategy which takes care of organizational survival, facing competition, decreasing the competition, improving the environment and minimizing the wastage without compromising quality and profit.
8	WOS process takes care social and environment at first by overlook the profit.	WOMS takes care organisational survival, sustainability and profit.

(d) White Ocean Mixed Strategy Model :

As discussed earlier, WOMS is a mixed strategy used by organizations to solve their problems optimally. The block diagram of White Ocean Mixed strategy model is shown in Fig. 3. The following steps are used while applying White Ocean Mixed strategy in an organization :

Step 1 : Identify organizational problem depending on the objective by studying situational opportunities.

Step 2 : Analyse the problem and predict best solution among possible solutions.

Step 3 : Decide the best strategy or mixture of strategy among available strategies including Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Green ocean Strategy, and Black Ocean strategy as White ocean strategy.

Step 4 : Implement the WOM strategy in organizational problem and ensure optimum solution.

Figure 3 : Block diagram of White Ocean Mixed strategy model.

V. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT STRATEGIES WITH WHITE OCEAN MIXED STRATEGY

White Ocean Mixed Strategy is compared with other individual strategies based on their characteristics and given in tables 3 – 6. In this section we have also compared White Ocean Mixed strategy characteristics with ideal Strategy characteristics and shown in table 7.

Table 3 : Comparison of Red Ocean Strategy and White Ocean Mixed Strategy.

S. No.	Red Ocean Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy
1	Position your company where the competitive forces are the weakest	Identify organizational problem depending on the objective by studying situational opportunities
2	Exploit changes in competitive forces	Choose a suitable strategy to face the problem
3	Reshape the forces in your favour	Implement the identified strategy to solve the problem optimally
4	Industry structure drives competition and profitability, not whether an industry is emerging or mature, high tech or low tech, regulated or unregulated.	Any type of industrial problem can be solved by studying industry, its environment, monitoring policies by choosing right strategy or mixture of strategy in right time
5	Provides competitive edge to the organization	Foresee the future and decide your strategy
6	Compete in existing market space	Prepare the preference sequence of problems and strategies
7	Beat the competition	Win the war without fighting
8	Make the value/cost trade-off	Nullify the challenge
9	Align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost	White ocean is a best strategy which contains mixture of other strategies depending the upon situations.

Table 4 : Comparison of Blue Ocean Strategy and White Ocean Mixed Strategy.

S. No.	Blue Ocean Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy
1	Reconstruct/cross market boundaries	Foresee and Identify problems in the way to win the challenges to fulfil the goal
2	Focus on big picture not numbers	Focus on the organizational objectives and problems
3	Reach beyond existing demand	Preference to solve the problem to reach objectives
4	Get the strategic sequence right	Prepare the preference sequence of problems and strategies
5	Create uncontested market space	Win the war without fighting
6	Makes the competition irrelevant	Nullify the challenge
7	Create and capture new demand	Foresee the future and decide your strategy
8	Break the value-cost trade-off	Bridge the survival and win concepts through proper plan & Implementation
9	Align whole system of firm's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost.	Align whole system of firm's activities in pursuit of survival & win
10	Blue Ocean is a good business strategy to generate idea, innovation and profit	White ocean is a best strategy which contains mixture of other strategies depending the upon situations

Table 5 : Comparison of Green Ocean Strategy and White Ocean Mixed Strategy.

S. No.	Green Ocean Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy
1	Decisions to improve the environment of a system	Decision to find the optimum solution to organizational problems
2	Long term sustainability	Long term sustainability
3	Decreasing risk on functioning of the system	Minimizing the risk by choosing suitable strategy.
4	Organizations which follow this strategy can expect long term sustainability with low profit	Organizations which follow mixed strategy can expect long term sustainability with high profit.
5	Green ocean strategy focus only on environmental sustainability. Hence it may not sustain in competition with other firms which follows blue ocean or red ocean strategies.	White ocean mixed strategy is a process of deciding optimum strategy a an organizational problem. It is survival strategy consisting of mixture of all other available strategies depending on situational constraints.

Table 6 : Comparison of Black Ocean Strategy and White Ocean Mixed Strategy.

S. No.	Black Ocean Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy
1	Identify a location where the environmental instabilities are lowest.	Identify the organizational processes where the problems are severe.
2	Exploit weakness of the controlling system/environment to overcome your organizations difficulty.	Identify the strength of the suitable strategy and the situational problem.
3	Control the problem and solve it in your favour.	Control the problem using suitable strategy
4	Ethical level of the Country drives the problems and solutions.	Experience and Intelligence of the executives chooses the suitable strategy or mixture of strategies
5	Provides confidence for sustainability through exploiting the weakness of the external controlling systems.	Provides confidence of winning the war without actually fighting by exploiting the opportunities
6	Solve the problems by en-cashing the weakness of the system	Solve the problem by adopting mixture of strategies depending on situation s
7	Negate the competition	Neutralize competition, encourage monopoly and sustainability by avoiding environmental degradation
8	Break ethics/value trade-off	Mix the suitable strategies to face the challenges
9	Show your existence by tapping the weakness of the system	Show your existence by en-cashing opportunities

Table 7 : Comparison of White Ocean Mixed Strategy with Ideal Strategy.

S. No.	Ideal Strategy	White Ocean Mixed Strategy
1	The strategy should be independent on types of business and type of problems.	Identify the organizational processes where the problems are severe.
2	The strategy should identify ideal solutions to organizational problems and fulfil organizational objectives	Identify the strength of the suitable strategy and the situational problem.
3	Ideal strategy provides solutions to all problems the organization is facing and gives expected output whatever may be the constraints of the business system	Control the problem using suitable strategy
4	Flexible to accommodate internal and environmental changes.	Experience and Intelligence of the executives chooses the suitable strategy or mixture of strategies.
5	Success through ideal strategy is measurable.	Provides confidence of winning the war without actually fighting by exploiting the opportunities.
6	Ideal strategy will not consume any resources while implementing.	Solve the problem by adopting mixture of strategies depending on situation.
7	Ideal strategy is easy to implement and supports to fulfil the objectives at zero cost and zero time without any constraints.	Neutralize competition, encourage monopoly and sustainability by avoiding environmental degradation.
8	Ideal strategy includes competitive strategy, monopoly strategy, sustainable strategy and survival strategy to win the organizational challenges.	Mix the suitable strategies to face the challenges and ensure winning.
9	Ideal strategy translates organizational business into ideal business.	WOM supports organizational existence by en-cashing opportunities.
10.	Ideal strategy guarantees the organizational success in any kind of internal and external environments.	Since WOM strategy is optimum strategy, it also ensures organizational success in any kind of internal and external environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

Various strategies are used in business organizations to ensure success in their objectives. Each strategies have their own limitations in global business scenario. In this paper, by studying the characteristics of ideal strategy, we have proposed a new strategy called White Ocean Mixed strategy which is an optimum strategy to solve organizational problems. The characteristics and the procedural steps of implementation of White Ocean Mixed Strategy in an organization is discussed. WOM strategy is compared with other individual strategies based on their characteristics and is also compared with ideal Strategy characteristics. WOM strategy is considered as optimum strategy the organizations can adopt to solve their problems to ensure success in their business.

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